

Durability Properties of Foamed Concrete with Fiber Inclusion

Authors : Hanizam Awang, Muhammad Hafiz Ahmad

Abstract : An experimental study was conducted on foamed concrete with synthetic and natural fibres consisting of AR-glass, polypropylene, steel, kenaf and oil palm fibre. The foamed concrete mixtures produced had a target density of 1000 kg/m³ and a mix ratio of (1:1.5:0.45). The fibres were used as additives. The inclusion of fibre was maintained at a volumetric fraction of 0.25 and 0.4 %. The water absorption, thermal and shrinkage were determined to study the effect of the fibre on the durability properties of foamed concrete. The results showed that AR-glass fibre has the lowest percentage value of drying shrinkage compared to others.

Keywords : foamed concrete, fibres, durability, construction, geological engineering

Conference Title : ICCCGE 2014 : International Conference on Civil, Construction and Geological Engineering

Conference Location : Istanbul, Turkey

Conference Dates : March 24-25, 2014